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SALES & DISTRIBUTION STRATEGIES: A COMPARISON OF BEST PRACTICES ADOPTED BY TOP TWO FMCG & DURABLE INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Bottom line success in your business hinges on sales execution. Your salespeople are your primary source of revenue. They are also your link to your customers. With this dual role, your sales force will need to be developed and supported. Make sure you keep them updated on company and industry information. Help them see customer satisfaction as a key goal. Your salespeople are the ones who are building the brand and contributing to its visibility. At the same time the word distribution may conjure up images of trucks loaded with boxes, but distribution is as much a sales and marketing issue as it is a delivery issue. We can define distribution as the method companies use to deliver products or services to their target market and channel as the means by which products or services are distributed, but these definitions hide an important truth. Your distribution channels are not only a means to ship your goods or deliver your services; they may also provide you with additional opportunities to sell your products. This is the simplest way you can explain Sales & Distribution. But now in the present commercial world it is more precisely termed as Logistics which is within the macro concept of Supply Chain Management which is more holistic in nature.

Corporate carry the burden of maximum benefit out of minimal cost or rather applied economics is the major portfolio of any management function. Hence Industries and corporate are on the lookout for latest, innovative, cost – effective measures to reach the nook and corner of a nation or the world. Corporates focus on making available the product to every citizen of a nation without the customers' spending on a halala on fuel. It means the products should be available within walk able or stone throw away distance. The extensive measure to establish a well-defined distribution network in providing goods/services to every part of the country, which leads to symbiotic benefit for the manufacturer and the consumer, is Sales Distribution. This study focus on the Sales Distribution networks of two corporate within FMCG & Consumer durable Industry on Indian perception.

Key words: *distribution, network, logistics, wholesale*

INTRODUCTION:

Pattern or structure of Sales Distribution or channels of distribution differ greatly between FMCG and consumer durable industry. Since the count of the inventory varies at large between the merchandise in these industry products, the reporting structures & the operating systems module differs at greater intensity. Due to these differences and the multitude stock count in FMCG, the companies under the industry focus on wholesale distributors for the network establishment. If discussed in detail of the differences between the sales distribution structures between FMCG & consumer durable industry are several. The first lesson was about innovation. Innovation and disruption is almost a daily phenomenon in the durables business. If one looks at FMCG categories, each category has gone through possibly six technology or innovation disruptions in the last 100 years. The second learning was around pricing. Prices in durables erode every month and every year as the large players in the industry cut product cost down by pushing scale. Price erosion has a direct impact on the way you think about costs. One realized that a business had to keep fixed costs low and convert as many fixed costs into variable cost as possible. The third lesson was around trade concentration and distribution. FMCG categories are distributed in millions of outlets and trade concentration is relatively low. Consumer electronics are available in about 40,000 outlets, the best distributed being DVDs and Colour Television. The durables business has strong local chains. These local chains have established a strong bond with their consumers over the last two decades

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starting by selling an iron box or a ceiling fan. These chains wield considerable influence over both the consumer and manufacturer. The reason they wield influence is simple.

What's important and what's not is not really understood in the durable circles is pricing. Pricing in FMCG is far more stable, consumers pay for the emotional surplus that the advertising aims to build. Easy interest finance has played a crucial role in getting durables into the urban households. Small town and rural easy financing is done by the durables trade at this point have a strong second hand market and that drives pricing, distribution and innovation strategy. Disruption in FMCG tends to come from superior advertising. And in a few cases, pricing. Disruption in Durables comes from technology, trade and constant price erosion. FMCG businesses seem like a walk in the park compared to durables. In the FMCG sector, the role of retail is to stock and make a brand visible since advertising does the rest. In durables, however, the retail point is likely the first source of information on product features, it is the place to experience the product and the feature, and it is also the place where the consumer goes back should she have a problem with her product. Managers coming from an FMCG background tend to underestimate trade influence in durables. If at all experts from panel of discussions gather to preview and forecast the problems in the distribution system of India they need to address the following questions and come out with related solutions on the same. How is the distribution system in the particular industry currently structured? What are the major changes that have occurred? What are the main issues in distribution that have been addressed in recent years? How has the company handled these issues? What are the factors that will affect the distribution system in the future? What are the challenges going forward? What is the thinking about how to address these challenges? How is retailing in India structured? What are the implications of foreign direct investment for Indian retailers? How is distribution performance measured? What is the scope of retail audit in India?

Procedure for selection of effective Marketing Channels

A General FMCG distribution Network

Sales Distribution Models: 1) Indian Tobacco Company (ITC)

ITC was established on August 24, 1910 as an Indian public conglomerate company headquartered in Kolkata, W Bengal. India ITC gross revenue for FY2013 stood at INR 43044 crores and market capitalization of INR 2, 44,245 crores. The company is currently headed by Yogesh Chander Deveshwar (Chairman) and it employs over 25,959 employees (HR figure from March 2013) at more than 60 locations across India.

One of the foremost in the private sector in terms of:

- Sustained value creation (BT-Stern Stewart survey)
- Operating profits
- Cash Profits

Only Indian FMCG Company to feature in Forbes 2000 List

- A comprehensive ranking of world’s biggest companies measured by a composite of sales, profits, assets & market value.
- Also ranked amongst the Top 10 global FMCG companies in terms of value creation during the period 2005-2009 by Boston Consulting Group.
- ITC is the only Indian company to feature consistently amongst the Top 10 global FMCG companies

The key Corporate strategies of ITC

- Focus on the chosen business portfolios of FMCG; Hotels; Paperboards, Paper & Packaging; Agri Business, Information Technology
- Blend diverse core competencies residing in various businesses to enhance the competitive power of the portfolio
- Position each business to attain leadership on the strength of world class standards in quality and costs
- Craft appropriate strategy of organization and governance process to :
 - Enable focus on each business and

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– Harness diversity of portfolio to create unique sources of competitive advantage

Distribution channel- ITC

SALES HIERARCHY OF ITC

RECRUITMENT & SELECTION

Sales Distribution Models: 2) Hindustan Unilever Limited (HUL)

The HUL's distribution network has evolved with time. The first phase of the HUL distribution network had wholesalers placing bulk orders directly with the company. Large retailers also placed direct orders, which 30 per cent of the total orders collected. The company salesman grouped all these orders and placed intent with the Head office. Goods were sent to these markets, with the company salesman as the consignee. The salesman then collected and distributed the products to the respective wholesalers, against cash payment, and the money was remitted to the company.

The Focus of the second phase, which spanned the decades of the 40s, was to provide desired products and quality service to the company's customers. In order to achieve this, one wholesaler in each market was appointed as "Registered Wholesaler," a stock point for the company products in that market. The company salesman still covered the market, canvassing for orders from the rest of trade. He then distributed stocks from the wholesaler through distribution units maintained by the company. The Registered Wholesaler system therefore increased the distribution reach of the company to a larger number of customers. The Highlight of the third phase was the concept of "Redistribution Stockiest (RS) who replaced the RS. The RS was required to provide the distribution units to company salesman. The second characteristic of the period was the establishment of the company depots system. This system helped in transshipment, bulk breaking and as a stock point to minimize the stock outs at the RS level. In the recent past a significant damage has been the replacement of the company depot by a system of third party carrying and forwarding agents(C&FAs) the C&FAs act as buffer stock points to ensure that stock outs did not take place. The C&FA system has also resulted in cost savings in terms of direct transportation and reduced time lag in delivery. The most important benefit has been improved customer service to the RS.

The role performed by the redistribution stockists includes: Financing stocks, providing warehouse facilities, providing manpower, providing service to retailers, implementing promotional activities, extending indirect coverage, reporting sales and stock data, demand stimulation and screening for transit damages. Presently the distribution system of HUL comprises of a distribution network of about 7000 redistribution stokists covering about one million retail outlets. The general trade comprises of grocery stores, chemists, wholesale, kiosks & general stores. HUL is using the POP method for much higher level of contacts, through in-store facilitators, sampling, education & experience.

Diagrammatic Distribution Network of HUL

Schematic distribution network of HUL

Rural Distribution Network of HUL

HUL reaches out to rural markets with ERP software:

In an effort to penetrate rural markets more effectively, Hindustan Unilever (HUL) is putting in place a mini enterprise resource planning (ERP) software system to empower 48,000 nationwide company volunteers (called Shakti ammas) who reach out to villages that the traditional HUL network does not service. In order to improve the efficacy of HUL’s Shakti entrepreneur programme, HUL deployed a low-cost mobile IT solution called Shakti DMS in 2012. The application also has updates on ongoing promotional and discount offers. This application takes into account the poor mobile coverage in rural India as well. It is built to work off-line. Shakti ammas are simply required to sync with the main server once a day after finishing their work,” according to HUL annual report 2012-13. The application, available in eight languages, allows Shakti ammas to take and bill orders and manage inventory. Project Shakti is a rural distribution initiative by HUL that targets small villages of less than 5,000 individuals. The Shakti ammas and Shaktimaans are unpaid employees of the company. HUL had earlier said Project Shakti contributes to 10 per cent of the company’s rural turnover nationally.

Consumer Durable Company: 1) SONY INDIA Ltd.

One of the most recognized brand names in the world today, Sony Corporation, Japan, established its India operations in November 1994, focusing on the sales and marketing of Sony products in the country. In a span of 19 years, Sony India has exemplified the quest for excellence in the world of digital lifestyle becoming the country's foremost consumer electronics brand. With relentless commitment to quality, consistent dedication to customer satisfaction and unparalleled standards of service, Sony India is recognized as a benchmark for new age technology, superior quality, digital concepts and personalized service that has ensured loyal customers and nationwide acclaim in the industry.

With brands names such as BRAVIA, Xperia, Alpha, Headphones, Handycam®, Cyber-shot, Xplod™, Sony hi-fi, Memory stick® and PlayStation®, Sony has established itself as a value leader across its various product categories of Audio/Visual Entertainment products, Information and Communications, Recording Media, Business and Professional products.

Sony India is one of the most recognized consumer electronics brand in the country, with a reputation for new age technology, digital concepts and excellent after sales service. In India, Sony has its footprint across all major towns and cities in the country through a distribution network comprising of over 20,000 dealers and distributors, more than 300 exclusive Sony outlets and 25 branch locations. Sony India also has a strong service presence across the country with 365 service outlets. Manned by customer friendly and informed sales persons, Sony's exclusive stores 'Sony Center' are fast becoming the most visible face of the company in India. A distinctive feature of Sony's service is its highly motivated and well-trained staff that provides the kind of attentive and sensitive service that is rare today.

Sony is committed to ensuring that both the products and the marketing activities employed truly make a difference to people's lifestyles and offer them new dimensions of enjoyment. Relentless commitment to quality, continuous dedication to customer satisfaction and unparalleled standards of service is what differentiates us from countless competitors and reflects a true image of all that is Sony. From time to time all companies rework their marketing / selling strategies & specially the innovations in the channels of distribution or more simply changes in distribution strategies. The main reasons of change and need to adapt for changes are due to the challenging market conditions and the entry of MNCs into the Indian soil on a day to day basis. In the thrust of MNC competition the national brands too thrive their best for existence. Another reason is the business environment where the competitors try out all marketing gimmicks, intelligent strategies and this calls for the vibrant business environments which in turn request for substantiated changes. A third reason is the strategic planning within the organization which can arise from economy policy changes, government tax policy changes, change in the governments, change in the management, higher profit needs, diversification needs etc. For a consumer durable company like SONY INDIA this also means redefining and reworking its retail format & strategy. For quite some time Sony India had been engaged in doing this.

The change in Sony India's retail strategy addresses all the requirements of different types of customers & outlets. As part of its sales strategy the company sells directly to retailers in four metropolitan cities – Delhi, Calcutta, Mumbai & Chennai & Bangalore, where the COD format is zero level from Manufacturer to retailer. In other cities & towns Sony India sells through its wholesale (1- level COD) distributors. The distributors supplies to multibrand retailers. Sony India's new retail strategy new retail strategy has four components such as

- a) Introduction of new retail format like Pro shop
- b) Upgrading existing Sony exclusive outlets and renaming as Sony Zone.
- c) Expanding the existing Sony outlets ;and
- d) The web initiative.

This structural design is based on Sony India's market analysis and finding that, as products become technically sophisticated, it is more of technology selling for companies at the retail level than simply selling the products/brands. Under the new retailing scheme/strategy. Pro shops will sell lifestyle products like home theatre and car audios through nationwide retail network. Sony Zone (upgraded format of earlier Sony

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Exclusive) will be smaller in size (compared to Sony world) and located in upcountry markets. Sony Zone outlets will only sell color televisions and audio products/models. Sony India plans to increase the number of Sony Zone to 500 from the present 29. Sony world will be franchised-based mega retail format-a one-stop shop for all Sony India products/brands. Each Sony world will cover a floor area of 3000-4000 sq.ft and centrally air conditioned with appropriate lighting to offer shopping comfort and pleasure. The plan of Sony India is to have one Sony outlet in all cities with a population of 10 Lakhs and more. This means establishing (through the franchise route) about 50 Sony world outlets in the country. Currently multi-brand outlets generate more than 80 per cent of Sony India's turnover.

Sony Worlds account for more than 10 per cent and Sony Exclusives/Sony Zones contribute the balance (7 to 8 per cent) turnover. With the introduction of Pro shops, restructuring/expansion of retail formats, these ratios will change more in favor of company's exclusive /franchised outlets. This will help the company to have better control over the operations of these outlets. The web initiative or the internet-enabled system, particularly in Sony worlds, will introduce more effectiveness to the operations. Sony India has plans to introduce to popularize Sony world. To achieve this, the company has intensified its retail promotion. It has doubled its ad spend on commercials- both TV channels and newspapers. This gives the required promotional support to Sony India's new retail strategy.

Consumer Durable Company: 2) Samsung INDIA Ltd.

Samsung India has segmented their products into five categories:

- 1) Mobile Phones
- 2) TV/Audio/Video
- 3) Camera/Camcorder
- 4) Home Appliances
- 5) PC/Peripherals/Printers

Distribution Channel:

Along with the launch of new products Samsung also consolidated its distribution system. Samsung had 18 state level distribution offices and a direct dealer interface. The direct dealer interface helped the company quick feedback from dealers and enabled to launch the products according to consumer needs. Samsung uses supply chain to enhance differentiation, increase sales and penetrate new markets & channels. Its supply chain is beneficial in several ways. It helps the company to deliver the goods & products to customer faster than expected. Its efficient supply chain is transparent, so that all the

players in the supply chain have the right information at the right time about the movement of the products within the chain. This means lower inventories, elimination of waste and reduction of costs. In addition the intangible benefits like quick feedback from customers in launching new products. To minimize time overruns, Samsung delivers its products directly from its factories to its regional dispatch centers (RDCs) and from there to dealers. Samsung has sales & service networks all over India and more than 650 service points. Samsung has implemented an innovative logistics system called Global Logistics Network system or on the other hand termed as the pivotal GLONETS which is unique and efficient. GLONET application is used on the B2B front for the vendors. This involves linking with key vendors, which constitute the bulk of the company's sourcing (26 domestic and 30 international vendors globally) through Samsung's GLONET. This system also enables the company to connect its purchase department with the Samsung HQ and international procurement offices through integrated ERP systems. The integrated ERP also enables the company to purchase its requirements from its international procurement offices and also from its Indian vendors. This application is also extended to order placement, production plan sharing and invoicing which would result and may lead to in- shorter business cycles and reduced inventory levels and low waste. In addition to GLONETS, Samsung also believes in JIT concept to its dealers. To make delivery of products within 48 hours of the expected date of delivery, the company has set up four RDCs, one at each regional location of the country. The distribution channel is structured very systematically wherein all the transactions and business conducted is documented. The program is based on incentives so that the dealer payments can be released on time. The company supplies its goods to the Star Elite who supplies goods to the distributor who in turn sell the goods via their own channel of retailers & distributors. The company brand shop network complements over 8500 retail points for Samsung products across the length and breadth of the country. Samsung plans to continue its penetration levels in the nation to reach out more and more Indian consumers. They consider the Star Elite partner as their actual product champion as their link with the end customer. As they have been adding value to the sale to the customer guiding him to the right purchase decision at a fair price.

Shop-in-shop

Samsung is enduring and ensuring a presence in almost all big malls & multiplexes even in the multi brand outlets, as the focus is to feel the presence in a shop-in-shop atmosphere.

Exclusive Showrooms :

Keeping its target customer to display Samsung products in a more lively and more life style ambience and to communicate the product benefits in a more interactive manner, SAMSUNG India has set up a wide spread network of over 100 exclusive showrooms comprising Samsung Digital Zone (focusing on high-end digital audio-video products such as MP3 players, camcorders and LCD/plasma TVs). The SAMSUNG digital home goes beyond the concept of a digital plaza or a brand shop in the digital home, they are trying to create a more interactive environment and providing a more lifestyle orientation to the display, so that the customer can visualize the products in his/ her own home settings. The company plans to supplement its existing SAMSUNG digital plazas (brand shops) by setting up Samsung digital homes in select cities. The company will also be creating exclusive Samsung corners in multibrand outlets this year. The demands and needs within the distribution channel lead to the establishment of mymemorystore.com. The site was more than an ordinary selling site, in fact it is an industry portal that allows the business partner to come in and track with the relevant industry information within the channel meaning minimizing the industry overhead. But now this site has closed due to some reasons. Samsung is also planning to invest over \$ I million in setting up a chain of exclusive units called Samsung talkies. The entire Samsung range including the latest handsets will be displayed at the outlets which will be set up in more than 10 cities across India including Bangalore, Mumbai and Hyderabad.

Samsung India Distribution Network

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